

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE'S ATTITUDE IN N.P.K.R.R CO-OPERATIVE SUGAR MILLS LIMITED AT THALAINAYAR

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Introduction

An attitude is a favorable or unfavorable evaluation of something. Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, things or event- this is often referred to as the attitude object. They reflect that how one feels about something. For example if someone says that I like my job. This statement expresses his attitude towards his job. Each and every person has a different attitude at different conditions. More precisely attitudes can be defined as a persistent tendency to feel and behave in a particular way toward some object which may include events or individuals as well. Attitude is a hypothetical construct that represents an individual's like or dislike for an item. Attitudes are positive, negative or neutral views of an "attitude object": i.e. a person, behaviour or event. People can also be "ambivalent" towards a target, meaning that they simultaneously possess a positive and a negative bias towards the attitude in question. Attitudes are composed from various forms of judgments. Attitudes develop on the ABC model (affect, behavioral change and cognition). The affective response is a physiological response that expresses an individual's preference for an entity. Attitudes towards supervision, pay, benefits, promotion, or anything that might trigger positive or negative reactions. As a result, employee satisfaction and attitudes represent one of the key areas for measuring organizational effectiveness. Attitudes are a mental state relative to what we believe and affects our entire lives. We express our attitude in our words and actions. Attitudes are greatly influenced by association which means they are contagious. The best way to develop a positive mental attitude is to surround yourself with optimists. Positive people have a magnetic influence which attracts help and support that assist them in achieving their goals.

Functions of Attitude

Adjustment

Attitudes often help people to adjust their work environment. Well treated employees tend to

develop a positive attitude towards their job, management and the organization in general while berated and ill treated organizational members develop a negative attitude. In other words, attitudes help employees adjust to their environment and form a basis for future behaviour.

Ego-Defensive

Attitudes help people to retain their dignity and self-image. When a young faculty member who is full of fresh ideas and enthusiasm, joins the organization, the older members might feel somewhat threatened by him.

Value-Expressive Function

Attitudes provide individuals with a basis for expressing their values. For example, a manager who values hard and sincere work will be more vocal against an employee who is having a very casual approach towards work.

Knowledge

Attitudes provide standards and frames of reference that allow people to understand and perceive the world around him.

Statement of the Problem

Attitudes are reasonably good predictors of behaviours. They provide clues to an employee's behavioural intention or inclinations to act in a certain way. Positive job attitudes help predict constructive behaviours; negative job attitudes help predict undesirable behaviours. In the world of work we are concerned with attitudes towards supervision, pay, benefits, promotions or anything that might trigger positive or negative reactions. Employee satisfaction and attitudes represent one of the key areas of measuring organizational effectiveness. This study is undertaken to analyze the employees' attitudes towards the organization in N.P.K.R.R. sugar mills Ltd.

Objectives

- * To know the employees' attitude towards the organization.
- * To know the reason for employees' positive attitude.

- * To know the reason for employees negative attitude.
- * To know the employees expectations from the organization.
- * To make suggestions to improve the attitudes of the employees to the management.

Methodology

Methodology conducting the research in the field of study, research design, source of data collection, questionnaire, sampling plan and statistical tools.

Research Design

Research design is purely and simply the framework or plan for a study that guides the collection and analysis of data. The research design indicates the methods of research i.e., that the method of gathering information and the method of sampling. The researcher has adopted 'Descriptive Design' for research studies. The major emphasis is to insights by the study.

Source of Data Collection

The researcher used 'Primary Source' of data collection; the data's are directly collected from the employees. The 'Secondary Source' of data collection is through books and websites.

Questionnaire

The data required for the study was collected through a questionnaire. The questionnaire contains two main sections solicits personal data about the employees. In the second section, the questions about the attitude of the employees. The data collected through such filled in questionnaire have been used for further analysis.

Sampling

The researcher adopted 'Convenient Sampling' method for the study. In this method, the researcher collected data from the employees belonging to various departments in a convenient manner. The researcher adopted this sampling method because it is simple to apply and analysis of data is reasonably easy.

Data Analysis And Interpretations

Table No . 1. Demographic profile of an employee

Gender	No. Of respondents	Percentage
Male	60	100
Female	0	0
Total	60	100
Age	No. Of respondents	Percentage
Below 25 years	0	0
26-35 years	10	17
36-45 years	20	33
Above 45 years	30	50
Total	60	100
Marital status	No. Of respondents	Percentage
Married	100	100
Unmarried	0	0
Total	60	100
Educational Qualification	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
SSLC	50	83
HSC	0	0
Diploma	6	10
UG	0	0
PG	4	7
Total	60	100

- ➔ Majority 60 respondents are male
- ➔ Majority 50% of the respondents are belongs to above 45 years, 33% of them are belongs to 36-45 years 17% of them are belongs to 26 – 35 years.
- ➔ All the respondents are married.
- ➔ Majority 83% of the respondents are quallified SSLC, 10% of the respondents are qualified Diploma, and only 7% of the respondents are qualified PG.

Table No . 2 Experience

Experience	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Below 5 years	0	0
5-10 years	0	0
11-15 years	8	13
Above 15 years	52	87
Total	60	100

Majority 87% of the respondents are getting an experience of above 15 years, and remaining 13% of the respondents are getting an experience of 11-15 years.

Table No . 3. Monthly Income

Monthly Income	No. Of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Below Rs. 5,000	0	0
Rs. 5,001-10,000	0	0
Rs. 10,001-15,000	10	17
Above Rs. 15,000	50	83
Total	60	100

Majority 83% of the respondents are earning monthly income of above 15,000, and remaining

Table No . 4. Types of Work Performed

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	14	23
Satisfied	46	77
Neutral	0	0
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 77% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied and 23% of them are highly satisfied.

Table No . 5. Working Hours

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Highly satisfied	28	47
Satisfied	28	47
Neutral	4	6
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 47% of the respondents are opinioned that they are highly satisfied with their working hours, 47% of them are satisfies and 6% are neutral.

Table No . 6. Responsibilities \ Assignments Given

Opinion	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	20	33
Satisfied	34	57
Neutral	6	10
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 57% of the respondents are responses that they are satisfied with their responsibility and assignments given, 33% of them are highly satisfied and remaining 10% of them are neutral with the their responsibilities.

Table No . 7. Treated by the Management

Opinion	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	20	33
Satisfied	30	50
Neutral	10	16
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 33% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with their management treated, 33% of them are highly satisfied and remaining 16% of them are neutral with their management treated.

Table No . 8. Recognition of Performance

Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	22	37
Satisfied	38	63
Neutral	0	0
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 63% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with the recognition of performance, and 37% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the recognition of performance.

Table No . 9. Job Security

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	34	57
Satisfied	26	43
Neutral	0	0
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 57% of the respondents are response that they are highly satisfied with Job security given by the organization, and remaining 43% of the respondents are satisfied with job security given by the organization.

Table No . 10. Work Stress

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	14	23
Satisfied	34	57
Neutral	12	20
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 57% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with the work stress, 23% of them are highly satisfied and 20% of them are neutral satisfied with their work stress.

Table No . 11. Grievance Redressal Procedures

Opinion	No. Of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Satisfied	46	77
Satisfied	14	23
Neutral	0	0
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
Total	60	100

Majority 77% of the respondents are responses that they are highly satisfied with the grievance redressal procedure given by the organization, 23% of them are satisfied with the grievance redressal procedure given by the organization.

Findings

- * Majority 60 respondents are male
- * Majority 50% of the respondents are belongs to above 45 years, 33% of them are belongs to 36-45 years 17% of them are belongs to 26 – 35 years.
- * All the respondents are married.
- * Majority 83% of the respondents are qualified SSLC, 10% of the respondents are qualified Diploma, and only 7% of the respondents are qualified PG.
- * Majority 87% of the respondents are getting an experience of above 15 years, and remaining 13% of the respondents are getting an experience of 11-15 years.
- * Majority 83% of the respondents are earning monthly income of above 15,000, and remaining
- * Nearly 77% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with the types of work performed by them`
- * Majority 47% of the respondents are opinioned that they are highly satisfied with their working hours, 47% of them are satisfies and 6% are neutral.
- * Nearly 57% of the respondents are responses that they are satisfied with their responsibilities and assignments given.

- * Majority 33% of the respondents are opinioned that they satisfied with their management treated.
- * Majority 63% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with the recognition of performance.
- * Nearly 57% of the respondents are response that they are highly satisfied with job security given by the organization.
- * Majority 57% of the respondents are opinioned that they are satisfied with the work stress.
- * 77% of the respondents are responses that they are highly satisfied with the grivance redressal procedure given by the organization.

Suggestion

- * Appreciation is a fundamental human need. Employees respond to appreciation expressed through recognition of their good work because it confirms their work is valued. When employees and their work are valued, their satisfaction and productivity rises, and they are motivated to maintain or improve their good work.
- * Management in this regard may identify the ways by which leave facilities may be increasing the number of paid holidays etc.
- * Job security is a potential tool for the motivation of the employees which in this study shows that, the employees have a positive attitude towards it. The management may take the employees understand that they are the partners of the business and the employee's organization life depends up on the constructive contributions made by them.
- * The management with regard to the medical facilities along with ESI may offer a minimal amount exclusively for the medical expenditure as a special package for different levels of employees. This may motivate them and restrict them to avail leave.

Conclusion

This study is based on the employee's attitude in N.P.K.R.R Sugar Mills Limited. From the research findings the employees are highly satisfied/satisfied in all the conditions like working hours, work load, job security, co-worker & supervisor relationship, safety procedures, grievance redressal procedures, etc.. It shows that the employees have the positive attitudes in that organization. Finally studies conclude that the employees have the positive attitudes in N.P.K.R.R Sugar Mills Limited, Thalainayar.

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